

Analysis on the path of labor identity regression among higher vocational college students in the context of professional attainment education

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Abstract:In order to improve the practical needs of professional attainment education, it is of great significance for higher vocational colleges to train the qualified practical talents who respect labor, care for the grass-roots and have a sense of responsibility in the process of strengthening their labor identity education. Faced with the lack of student labor identity in higher vocational colleges, combined with the Marxist Theory of labor and human rights, this paper proposes the path to realize the regression of labor identity in higher vocational college students, so as to provide reference for further promoting and innovating professional attainment education in higher vocational colleges.

Key words:Higher vocational colleges; Labor identity; Marxism; Labor rights.

Publication online:15 August,2020

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To adapt to socialist market economy, it is an important task for higher vocational colleges to cultivate high-quality practical talents with both mental and physically health in line with the modernization construction. However, while in the process of cultivating and practicing the education of socialist labor concept, higher vocational students deviate from their object in terms of labor identity, which leads to the lack of self-responsibility and trust in their study, life, career selection and employment. The concept of labor is the important content advocated by the socialist core values, based on this, this paper has a deep understanding of the importance of vocational students' labor identity training with the general background of professional attainment education,

it makes an in-depth analysis of Marxist Theory of labor and human rights, and puts forward the reconstruction of vocational students' labor identity regression path, thus to further promote the enrichment and development of professional attainment education.

I. The significance of strengthening the students' labor identity education for higher vocational colleges

For the new period, labor identity education is a specific requirement for cultivating students' comprehensive qualities such as labor skills and personal cultivation. The significance of labor creating value goes beyond the actual value created by labor. Through labor, human beings not only obtain the necessary material instruments of production, but also gain the internal law hidden. From the perspective of higher vocational college students, the labor identity education with the professional attainment education as the core is conducive to improve their cognition of career development, and establishing a correct concept of professional ethics. In this way, they are able to develop their skills and enrich their spiritual life in the frontline.

1. Labor identity education is the innate need of qualified higher vocational college students

With the development of China's socialist economy, the requirements for the professional quality of workers

are getting increasingly higher. As a vital talent resource in social and economic construction, vocational college students' labor identity education is obviously very necessary once they want to give full play to their great potential and fulfill their self-survival needs while satisfying their spiritual pursuit. Intellectual progeny, admittedly, it is important to implement quality education and make students happy in life, but it should not be the only way. People earn their living by working, while labor impels us to physical, intellectual, and moral perfection. Vocational college students improve their ability to create, appreciate, feel and enjoy beauty in labor, such to make its primary function of earn living to an inevitable course of getting a decent life. Therefore, to accept the education of labor identification and to participate in labor practice, not only helps to improve students' strong will to live independently, to overcome difficulties and to adapt to the society, but also helps to cultivate students' collectivism and frugal character..

2. Labor identity education is effective to implement ideological and political education in higher vocational colleges

2017 Opinions on Strengthening and Improving Ideological and Political Education in Campus with New Forms emphasizes that, it is necessary to band together the solution of practical problems and ideological problems, increase the practical teaching, organize more social practice activities, strengthen the construction of practical teaching bases, and improve the practice and training system. For higher vocational colleges, labor identity education should be the entry point of ideological and moral education in higher vocational education. In combination with the characteristics of training technical talents in higher vocational colleges and the ideological problems of current students, labor itself is an effective method to integrate the thought of labor identity into the education and teaching practice, which is much better than the direct theory lecture. China's higher vocational education is facing new problems and challenges

in its development. Some colleges and universities, when they advocate the teaching concept of technical education, show up negligence on the quality education, especially in the cultivation of socialist moral goals in labor education. Hence, in the context of professional attainment education, strengthening the labor identity education of higher vocational students not only means great guiding significance for the cultivation of correct ideology, it is also an effective way for higher vocational colleges to strengthen the ideological and political education.

3. Strengthening labor identity education is an inevitable requirement for practicing socialist core values

Opinions on cultivating and practicing Socialist Core Values explicitly put forward “to integrate the cultivation and practice of socialist core values into the whole process of national education”, to make the socialist core values run through the fields of basic education, higher education, vocational and technical education, and implement it in all aspects of education and teaching, so as to form an effective form and a long-term mechanism for young students to study hard, love labor and support the motherland. With the common characteristics of talent training in general higher education, in addition, higher vocational colleges have their own peculiarities of professionalism, practicality, etc., they require highly for professional skills. Therefore, higher vocational students, facing to multiple objects and complex labor process, must strengthen the learning of vocational skills, they shall attach great importance to the objective requirement of strengthening the education of labor concept put forward by the socialist core values, this is an indispensable part to realize comprehensive improvement of people, society, nation, as well as the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

II . Professional attainment education in higher vocational colleges should make

clear that labor is the ultimate root of

Professional quality refers to the comprehensive quality and ability of professional ethics, consciousness, behavior and professional skills that employees display in their actual study and work, and it is an important indicator to measure whether professionals can adapt to and be competent for the corresponding jobs. While receiving the vocational skill training, higher vocational college students present a weak awareness of learning due to the lack of labor identity. And in the process of job selection and employment, there are many problems such as self-centeredness and improper professional attitude. How to strengthen the cultural connotation construction of higher vocational colleges and how to improve the vocational quality of higher vocational students, these have become the foci and difficultie in the training of higher vocational talents. We believe that professional attainment education with the theme of "labor is the initial root of human nature" should be emphasized while strengthening the professional cultivation of vocational college students.

1. Enhance the cultivation of students' labor consciousness

In view of the over-indulgence of parents and the lack of cultivation resources of vocational quality in higher vocational colleges, some students have a poor concept of labor and independent ability, often followed by phenomena such as neglecting work, being lazy and lax, and avoiding collective activities. The cultivation of labor consciousness creates excellent personality, forms corresponding sense of responsibility and creativity, meanwhile, it has extremely important significance for the development of individual intelligence. As a practical process of interaction between subjects and objects, labor created human beings and changed the world, it has also become the source of the continuous development of human civilization. As the spiritual aspect of transforming the object to meet the innate needs of self and social development, labor consciousness

contains not only the value judgment of labor subject but also the value choice of labor subject. In the course of human history, "what is the nature of man?" this has always been the fundamental question of inquiry in the field of education and science. And the correct understanding of the root of human nature -- labor -- is related to the realization of human's free and comprehensive development, which is also the key to higher vocational students to establish a noble labor professional quality. "Who am I?" "What is the real purpose of learning vocational skills (namely, labor)?" These should be considered as an important part of the entrance education of higher vocational students.

2. Properly recognize the importance of uniting manual labour with mental labor

In the narrow sense, labor is biased towards manual labour, while the modern "labor" in the broad sense has the dual direction of manual labour and mental labor. There are differences between these two kinds, but jobs make all equal. Labor is not just a means of making a living, besides, it is also an important part of people's world view, outlook on life and values. After entering the university, vocational college students cannot properly recognize the equal importance of manual and mental labor, they usually ignore the effect of manual labour in the process of their own growth, and often separate themselves from the working masses, even look down upon farmers, workmen and other manual workers. When it comes to employment, some graduates choose jobs in terms of the "leisure degree", and ignore the goal programming of their career development, put aside the career aspirations for the sake of money, take the priority of wage level to measure the quality of work, they frequently hit a brick wall in the job search and often seek for new jobs. Influenced by social public opinion, these phenomena easily lead to the whole social masses to seek profits and avoid responsibilities, to turn into pleasure-seeking; on the other hand, they also cause the social trust crisis to the students group. Marx once said: "the first historical action

of individuals to distinguish themselves from animals is not that they have ideas, but that they begin to produce their own means of livelihood."^{[1]P.(67)} Through the practice of labor and the use of complex production tools, human beings have been constantly transform nature, to actively adapt to nature and realize the liberation of human beings from nature. Therefore, in the process of cultivating vocational skills for vocational college students, they should be positively guided to recognize the importance of the unification of manual labour and mental labor.

3. Properly recognize the social attribute of labor

Now, most of the higher vocational students, the only children, who were grown up alone in a social environment, parents' doting education often leads to their generation of individual-oriented thought. They put too much emphasis on the realization of individual self-worth while too little on the collective sense of responsibility, mission and honor, which makes it difficult to adapt to the changes in collective life. Only with the correct understanding of the sociality of labor, can higher vocational students take the socialist collectivism spirit as the foundation of learning and life, can they closely link themselves with the masses, and can they truly apply their learned skills to the society. We can get a correct understanding of the human beings only via the social relations. Labor is both an individual activity and a social activity. It creates human beings, as well as the human society. Everyone is a member of the society. In the era with reform and innovation as the cores, diversified social values have an increasing impact on students. In the process of skill training and employment selection, higher vocational college students need to properly handle the relationship between the collective and the individual, the cooperation and competition. We are not living in a closed society that solves problems on its own, but an interconnected, multifaceted one. In the transition period, utilitarianism, money worship, and hedonism have a negative social significance on higher vocational students. If we always put

the maximization of personal interests as the guidance and such evaluation principle, higher vocational students may be separated from the society and the working masses, which will touch severely the quality of modern professional quality cultivation.

III. Take the foundation of Marx's labor rights theory to realize the regression of higher vocational students' labor identity

Because the nature of the school is different from that of ordinary colleges and universities, and the low social recognition of higher vocational college students, they often suffer great physical and mental pressure after entering the school. Most students are worried about their future and prospect. These students' self-evaluation and identity are relatively lower than those of ordinary college students, and they show a serious lack of self-confidence in life, study, employment and career guidance. How to realize the regression of labor identity in higher vocational colleges? We believe, in the process of vigorously advocating the labor concept education of the socialist core values, we must take the Marx labor rights theory as the foundation, strengthen the labor rights concept education in higher vocational colleges, thus to form the cultural atmosphere of respecting labor, caring for the grass-roots, narrowing the gap, such that the regression of labor identity of higher vocational college students can be realized.

1. Take Marx's theory of labor and human rights as the supreme guiding principle

For the moment, the weak recognition of labor value in higher vocational college students, their contempt for labor and even contempt for the working grass-roots are ubiquity. The reason lies in, first, before entering the university, the

higher pressure and heavy learning tasks squeeze out the required labor values education. Strengthening the cultivation of vocational quality of higher vocational college students and forming a good cultivation atmosphere is significant to evaluate the achievement of students' employment, entrepreneurship and the school's honorary image. Therefore, we think that the Marxist theory of labor and human rights should be taken as the supreme guiding principle while training the highly skilled talents in line with the socialist modernizationⁱ.

Labor human right is the theory and doctrine to explain human rights and social rationality in labor. Only labor right, which conforms to Marx's original intention, is of the entire Marxist theoretical foundation.^[2] The issue of labor rights involves the question of original rationality. Why should we protect and respect the rights and interests of laborers in labor? It is based on labor human rights. Whether from the legal or political perspective, this problem, should be ultimately illustrated in labor and labor rights.^[3] When exploring the problem of human nature, Marx took labor as its ultimate root, dragged the giver of human rights from the god back to human itself, and found the basis for the historical development of human society and human liberation in the real society. Our search for human rights will be ended once followed the doctrine of natural rightsⁱⁱⁱ.

Marx's theory of labor rights holds that labor is the essence of human.

beings, and labor expresses the essence through the supreme rule of human rights. Hence, labor will eventually realize the freedom and comprehensive liberation of human beings while creating human society. In Marx's view, all rights are all rooted in labor, without work, rights and dignity are lost; the ultimate explanation for any rationality in human society is labor. Marx believes that human rights are generated in the historical development, rather than natural. Through labor, humans obtain the rights while realize their

own liberation. Everyone's labor is a material production labor under specific historical conditions, and subject to certain social relations. Human and labor are inseparable, without labor, all human civilization would not be produced. When implementing the students' vocational skills cultivation, higher vocational colleges must put the Marxist Theory of labor and human rights as the supreme guiding principle of human rights, in the field of ideological and political education, as well as psychological health education, it is necessary to strengthen the education of Marx's labor rights theory, to make the students establish the real Marxist labor view and have a deep understanding of "labor is the only source of human rights", thus to promote the labor viewpoint formation of loving work, respecting work, caring for the grass-roots, and promoting frugality.

2.The core orientation is respect for labor

The freedom and equality of human come from labor, labor creates human himself, which is the concentrated embodiment of human nature. The state strongly emphasizes vocational quality education, in such context, higher vocational college students should enhance the value education of respecting labor in the course of learning relevant theoretical skills. The defeat of labor identity and lack of self-confidence, rooted in the disrespect for labor. "The respect for labor advocated by the socialist core value is to understand the status and function of labor from the perspective of the production mode and the human essence.^[4] Respect for labor is for oneself, while paying attention to the cultivation of high-quality practical talents in line with the needs of social and economic development, higher vocational colleges should strengthen the ideological and political theory education, publicize the Marxist Theory of labor and human rights, we should not forget to strengthen the professional attainment education with respect to labor as the core when focusing on the vocational skills education. So, the first step of positive significance will be taken in the reconstruction of students' labor value recognition in higher

vocational colleges.

3. The foundation of value is caring for the grass-roots

Respect for labor is the most fundamental core proposition of socialism. The rationality of the values, like liberty, equality, fraternity, justice and honesty in socialist society are illustrated via labor. As a disadvantaged group, higher vocational college students should be generally respected and recognized by the public. The society and employers should not take the academic record as the only indicator to measure the ability of students, we should not lower the recognition degree of students in higher vocational colleges only by virtue of their educational background. Colleges and society should give more attention to the lack of their labor identity and more reasonable care to the grass-roots on the premise of abiding by respecting labor. Of course, unlike in some countries, we can't simply leave the labor and show humanitarian concern to the grass-roots, the adaptive choice is to give the most extensive care through Marx's labor theory of human rights, such to boost higher vocational college students to become high-quality talents who make living by labor, who obtain a comprehensive and free development and conform to the social need of high-quality talents⁶.

4. The effective way is to narrow the gap

In the primary stage of socialism, all members work for making a living in general. Socialism has eliminated exploiting classes systems, nevertheless, social inequality and division of labor continues to exist, and the differences in society are not comb-out yet. The primary stage of socialism allows such differences, but it does not mean that the differences can be unlimited expanded. The undisputed differences between human beings caused by natural factors, such inevitable differences like differences between a person with cerebral palsy and a genius, however, will develop into the non-inevitable differences in the process of

human labor. Socialism should first take effective measures to narrow differences through human union and other means. For example, while genius creates great wealth for the world, he can also create a comfortable working environment for congenital cerebral palsy infants by tax, charity and voluntary. Higher vocational students, as the nature of the school and the lower level of education than the undergraduate academies, they gain weaker social recognition, so there is the existence of the so-called "difference". To solve this problem, our family, school and society should encourage every higher vocational student to give full play to his own potential, and constantly narrow the non-inevitable differences, thus to realize the free and comprehensive development of human beings. Once in the vocational skills development, higher vocational college students can make continuous efforts, always take Marx's labor rights theory as the guiding principle, continuously tap their potential, set up correct labor values, keep pursuing Marxist ideal of labor values. In this way, their lack of labor value identity will be broken by their contribution to society; on the other hand, they will experience the real happiness in the labor.

In conclusion, in the context of professional attainment education and in the modern Chinese society guided by the socialist core values, to solve the lack of labor identity of higher vocational college students the joint efforts of various parties are essential to continuously innovate the educational and teaching concepts of higher vocational colleges, finally the ideal results can be achieved.

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- ⁶Professor He Yunfeng discussed this topic in detail in several academic papers. See his work From Decent Work to Free Labor -- On the Change of Labor in China published in Exploration and Free Views and Labor Is the Root of Socialist Freedom, Equality, Human Value and Dignity published in Journal of Youth.

⁶The concept of labor rights mentioned is not the concept of laborers' rights in the sense of

jurisprudence, but the ontological concept of human rights which is opposite to the natural rights in the sense of metaphysics.

ⁱⁱⁱAlthough the idea of natural rights saved people from the theological oppression in the middle ages, human are indeed human, not gods. The theory of natural rights ascribes human rights to god, which in essence is just a powerful tool for capitalism to oppose feudal nobility and theology with the help of god, such that realize its ruling purpose.

^{iv}The humanitarianism propagated by capitalism started from the spirit of the Renaissance in the 15th century, while its goal is to spread the ancient Greek and Roman culture, and make human talents to full play. It once played an important role in the struggle of capitalism against feudalism and religionism, but its nihilism and pessimism is an abstract humanitarian concept, which is fundamentally different from Marxist humanism in safeguarding people's dignity and rights.